

Top Research on Applied Linguistics in Iran

by

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- 1 Al Shalabi, M. F., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Personality theory and TESOL. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 3(1), 14-22.

In this paper, Al Shalabi and Salmani Nodoushan (2009) argued, based on evidence from psychological literature, that there are three major approaches to the study of personality, namely (1) situationism, (2) interactionism, and (3) constructivism. It is also noticed that these approaches have resulted in the emergence of three major types of personality theories: (i) type theories, (ii) trait theories, and (iii) factor theories. In connection to TESOL, it is argued that extroversion/introversion and risk-taking are the most important personality factors. It is also argued that such personality factors as tolerance of ambiguity, empathy, self-esteem, inhibition, and intelligence have been addressed by TESOL research, but that the two most important factors are extroversion/introversion and risk-taking.

- 2 Allan, K., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Pragmatics: The state of the art (An online interview with Keith Allan). *International Journal of Language Studies*, 9(3), 147-154.

This interview was conducted with Professor Keith Allan with the aim of providing a brief but informative summary of the state of the art of pragmatics (Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). In providing answers to the interview questions, Professor Allan begins with a definition of pragmatics as it is practiced today, i.e., the study of the meanings of utterances with attention to the context in which the utterances are made. He further notices that discourse analysis, pragmatics, semantics, semiotics, and the philosophy of language are related disciplines, but unlike some other scholar, he does not distinguish 'texts' from 'discourses' in that he sees texts to be the interesting products of discourse. Later, in the course of the interview, he accepts the interviewers' chronological approach to pragmatics, but suggests that any historian of pragmatics would have his or her own version. Further, in his response to a question concerning Mey's Pragmatic Act Theory (PAT), Professor Allan quotes from Mey (2001) to presents a view of pragmemes and practs. He further suggests that there is no bound on the number of possible hypotheses (theories) of language structure and usage, and that all theories are worthy of

consideration provided that rational grounds can be advanced for the assessment of different hypotheses. The future direction of pragmatics, in Professor Allan's view, will rely on corpora in that corpora provide bodies of naturally occurring texts which can be used to test any theoretical claims in pragmatics.

- 3 Bhatia, V. K., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Genre analysis: The state of the art (An online interview with Vijay Kumar Bhatia). *International Journal of Language Studies*, 9(2), 121-130.

In this interview (Bhatia & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015), Vijay Bhatia freely reflects on his personal experiences, perceptions, and views about the development of Genre Analysis in the early eighties towards Critical Genre Analysis today. He offers his impressions about how professionals construct, interpret, use and often exploit generic resources in their everyday practice to meet their professional objectives in specific contexts. Starting from the early conceptualization of Genre in the eighties in the United Kingdom, he points out how it was essentially inspired by the everyday concerns about the teaching and learning of English for Specific Purposes, and how it continued to gain popularity and is considered one of the most popular frameworks for ESP applications in the present-day context. However, he points out, it is not enough to analyze and describe just the specialist discourses; it is also equally important to understand how such discourses are employed in professional practice to meet specific requirements of a particular profession. Hence the need to develop traditional Genre Analytical framework further towards what he calls Critical Genre Analysis to demystify interdiscursive performance in specific academic and professional settings.

- 4 Birjandi, P., Alavi, S. M., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2004). *Advanced writing*. Tehran: Zabankadeh publications.

Advanced Writing (Birjandi, Alavi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2004) is the first in a series of books designed to develop the expository and argumentative writing skills that EFL learners need to express their ideas effectively. Through highly illustrative examples, model paragraphs, and carefully constructed exercises, students complete, step by step, activities which enable them to understand and fully appreciate in the writing process. Units one, two, and three will familiarize the students with the rudiments, format, and overall structure of the paragraph; unit four deals with techniques of support; units five through eleven deal with the rhetorical patterns most commonly found in expository writing (enumeration, chronology, process, description, definition, cause and effect, and comparison and contrast); unit twelve treats argumentation not as a rhetorical device in and of itself, but rather as a kind of writing which often employs a variety of rhetorical devices; finally, unit thirteen provides a number of dos and don'ts that enable the university students to revise and enhance their paragraphs. The effective course-book/workbook format provides students with a powerful five-step approach to paragraph writing. Students will accomplish the following tasks that lead to clear, effective, and concise paragraphs: Deduction: the initial step, in

which the internal structures of different kinds of paragraphs are discussed. Exposure: the second step, in which students read at least a model paragraph. Analysis: the third step, in which students gain greater understanding of the structure of the model paragraph. Planning: the fourth step, in which students make outlines for their own paragraphs based on their understanding of the models. Writing: the final step, in which students write original full paragraphs. The book covers the fundamental techniques and methods of paragraph writing, yet the format allows the teacher to insert additional exercises and assignments that are both class-specific and provide for the individual teacher emphasis. This flexibility should give the experienced teacher a focus for materials and the newer teacher a pedestal on which to build. Because the course is based on paragraph writing, it does not pay much attention to grammatical structures. Naturally, EFL students, even at the advanced level, continue to have grammatical weaknesses. Advanced Writing deals with grammar problems that are specifically related to paragraph writing: punctuation, sentence structure, and so forth. The grammatical explanations are, however, very concise because the book focuses on paragraph development. The ultimate goal of the book is to make sure that students finish their paragraph writing course with knowledge of the format of expository and argumentative paragraphs. Throughout Advanced Writing students are encouraged to write about topics that interest them, and are motivated to become fully engaged in the writing process. They are also persuaded to develop effective techniques for effective, clear, and concise paragraphs.

- 5 Brown, J. D., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Language testing: The state of the art (An online interview with James Dean Brown). *International Journal of Language Studies*, 9(4), 133-143.

In this interview (Brown & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015), JD Brown reflects on language testing/assessment. He suggests that language testing can be seen as a continuum with hard core positivist approaches at one end and post-modernist interpretive perspectives at the other, and also argues that norm referencing (be it proficiency, placement, or aptitude testing) and criterion referencing (be it diagnostics, progress, or achievement testing) fall on this continuum. He further suggests that evaluation is done at the level of program or course but that assessment is focused on the classroom, and then argues that both assessment and evaluation exploit measurement and testing albeit to different effects. He then comments on his views about high-stakes and low-stakes testing as well as washback, and finally expresses serious concerns about the impacts of language policy on language testing by calling the current NS models into question. Relating his concerns to validity issues, he suggests that language testers need to consider other options to the NS model to serve the needs of speakers of other Englishes.

- 6 Capone, A., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). On indirect reports and language games: Evidence from Persian. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 8(2), 26-42.

Approaching (indirect) reports from Wittgenstein's perspective on language games, and evaluating them with an eye on Sperber and Wilson's Relevance Theory (RT), this paper by Capone and Salmani Nodoushan (2014) draws on evidence from Persian to support Capone's Paraphrasis/Form Principle (PFP). It begins with a brief but informative review of relevant works on reported speech—including Davidson's Paratactic view of indirect reports, Wittgenstein's notion of language games, Sperber and Wilson's relevance theory, Weizman and Dascal's theory of clues and cues, and Lepore and Anderson's views about slurs. It then goes on to show how Capone's Paraphrasis/Form Principle (PFP) functions as a more explanatorily adequate account of reported speech. In doing so, it describes how (indirect) reports are performed in Persian. The paper cites relevant examples from Persian to show that a semantico-pragmatic explanation of reported speech—like Capone's PFP—is more robust in adequately explaining the notion of 'samesaying' which lies at the heart of (indirect) reporting. Of utmost importance is the paper's attempt at showing how 'insincere' reporting through linguistic manipulations—like topicalization—can transform social realities.

- 7 Johns, A. M., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). English for Specific Purposes: The state of the art (An online interview with Ann M. Johns). *International Journal of Language Studies*, 9(2), 113-120.

This forum paper is based on a friendly and informative interview conducted with Professor Ann M. Johns (Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). In providing answers to the interview questions, Professor Johns suggests that all good teaching is ESP, and also distinguishes between EOP and ESP in that the former entails much more "just in time" learning while the latter may be directed more at "just in case." She further adds 'context' as the sixth enduring conception to the list of the five concepts which, according to Swales (1990), underlie ESP. She further suggests that (a) Register Analysis, (b) Rhetorical Discourse Analysis, (c) Target Language Use Situation Analysis, and (d) Genre Analysis have had a major role in the development of ESP. As for CBI or CLIL, she suggests that there is much more to ESP than content, and emphasizes that ESP can account for the changing needs of learners in the twenty-first century by employing effective on-going needs assessment and target situation analysis. Towards the end of the interview, she presents her views on the future direction of ESP by suggesting that more serious research into target situations is needed, and invites ESP specialists to be more open, flexible, and sensitive to context.

- 8 Karami, H., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). Differential item functioning (DIF): Current problems and future directions. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 5(3), 133-142.

With the rising concerns over the fairness of language tests, Differential Item Functioning (DIF) has been increasingly applied in bias analysis (Karami & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011). Despite its widespread use in psychometric

circles, however, DIF is facing a number of serious problems. This paper is an attempt to shed some light on a number of the issues involved in DIF analysis. Specifically, the paper is focused on four problems: the inter-method indeterminacy, the intra-method indeterminacy, the ad hoc interpretations, and the impact of DIF on validity. In order to orient the reader, the paper also provides a brief introduction the fundamental concepts in DIF analysis.

- 9 Karami, H., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). The impact of analogy on L3 reading comprehension. *The Reading Matrix: An International Online Journal*, 14(1), 112-120.

Karami and Salmani Nodoushan (2014) argue that little research has been conducted to investigate the effect of analogy on third language (L3, hereafter) reading comprehension though some experts believe that it has facilitating and debilitating effects on L1 and L2 respectively. This article intends to explore the effect of analogies on reading comprehension of expository texts by students of English as a third language. Subjects were all Turkish university students of English as a Foreign Language who had Farsi as their second language. Written recall protocols taken from 350 participants were analyzed for a text with and without analogy. The results indicated that analogy had a facilitative effect regardless of proficiency level.

- 10 Kazemi, A., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2017). An Analysis of the Opening and Closing Verses in the Holy Quran. *Proceedings of AICS-Social Sciences*. Syiah Kuala University, Banda Aceh, Aceh, Indonesia (October 18-20, 2017)

Applying a conversation-analytic framework to Quranic verses and chapters, Kazemi and Salmani Nodoushan's (2017) qualitative study sought to shed new lights on the opening and closing verses in The Holy Quran. In effect, the study analyzed the opening and closing verses of 14 surahs to find out the central themes upon which they begin and come to a close. The analysis was conducted using the Persian translations of the verses as well as seeking help from the available Quran commentary or exegesis written in English. The analysis of the opening verses of the selected surahs revealed three central themes: (1) some surahs begin with words that praise and eulogize Allah, (2) some with imperative sentences or commandments addressed to the Holy Prophet, and (3) some related to specific events and times. Regarding the closing verses, the findings were not uniform across the selected surahs; while in some surahs the closing verses together with the opening verses deal with a similar topic or theme, in some other surahs the closing verses are concerned with different topics.

- 11 Kazemi, A., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018). A conversation analytic perspective on Quranic verses and chapters. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 5(1), 1-11.

Applying a conversation-analytic framework to Quranic verses and chapters, Kazemi and Salmani Nodoushan's (2017) qualitative study sought to shed new lights on the opening and closing verses in The Holy Quran. In effect,

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- 12 Nemati, M., Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Ashrafzadeh, A. (2010). Learning strategies in proficient and less proficient readers in medicine. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 4(2), 19-32.

The study by Nemati, Salmani Nodoushan and Ashrafzadeh (1010) aimed to diagnose the probable significant differences in the use of language learning strategies among medical-text readers of opposite sex from different levels of proficiency. 120 (N=120) participants were randomly selected from Azad Medical University of Mashhad: 60 medical students (age range 23-25; 30=male and 30=female) and 60 professors (age range 45-55; 30=male and 30=female). They took the Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) questionnaire. Their responses to the 50 items on the questionnaire were totaled and sets of scores were obtained for overall, direct, indirect, memory, cognitive, compensative, metacognitive, social, and affective strategies. Independent samples 't'-tests were performed for the analysis of the data. Results after analysis of the data showed that male and female respondents in each proficiency group used the same learning strategies. However, as far as individual direct and indirect sub-strategies are concerned, two significant differences were found: (i) male and female proficient readers used compensative strategies differentially, with females using these strategies more frequently; The same also held for less proficient readers, but in this case, it was the male group that used these strategies more frequently; and (ii) only in the case of proficient readers did male readers use affective strategies more frequently. Keywords: English for Medical Purposes, Learning Strategies, ESP, Language Strategies, SILL.

- 13 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (1992). A review of diploma English exam. *The FLT Journal (Roshd)*,34/35, 14-19. [Persian Text]

In this paper, Salmani Nodoushan (1992) reviews the main problems that are found in construct of Iranian high school diploma English exam. The text of the paper is in Persian

- 14 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (1995). *A sociopragmatic comparative study of ostensible invitations in English and Farsi* (Unpublished Master's Thesis). University of Isfahan, Isfahan, Iran.

In his master's thesis, Salmani Nodoushan (1995), states that, of late, linguistics has been trying to come up with a universal theory of language. Linguists, sociolinguists, and psycholinguists have focused on the different aspects of language. The sum of all their efforts has, no doubt, contributed to the developing field of Universal Grammar. However, the field calls for a good number of other research projects in the different languages of the world. As such, the present study was carried out with the aim of examining Farsi ostensible invitations in terms of the universals of pragmatics. To this end, 45 field workers observed and reported 566 ostensible and 607 genuine invitations. 34 undergraduates were interviewed and afforded 68 ostensible and 68 genuine invitations. And, 41 pairs of friends were interviewed and afforded 41 ostensible invitations. The data were then put to statistical tests: the comparison of ratios was carried out for the purposes of comparing the ratios of the two types of invitations (for any probable difference) in terms of the seven features that control their use in the English language; the chi-square test was also carried out to determine whether the type of invitation was dependent on such variables as the sex, age, and social class of the inviters or not. The results of the data analysis revealed that Farsi ostensible invitations go by the universal norms that influence language use. It was also concluded that the type of invitation was dependent on the variables mentioned above.

- 15** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (1998). Correlation in language testing. *The Research Quarterly of Arak Islamic Azad University, 1*, 139-142. [Persian Text]

In this paper, Salmani Nodoushan (1998) reviews the main roles that correlation coefficient plays in test development. The paper focuses on reliability, validity, and common variance. The text of the paper is in Persian

- 16** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2002). *Text-familiarity, reading tasks and ESP test performance: A study on Iranian LEP and Non-LEP university students* (Unpublished PhD Dissertation). University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran.

In his Ph.D. dissertation, Salmani Nodoushan (2002) studies the effects of text familiarity, task type, and language proficiency on university students' LSP test and task performances. 541 senior and junior university students majoring in electronics took the TBRT (Task-Based Reading Test). Variance analyses indicated that text familiarity, task type, and language proficiency, as well as the interaction between any given pair of these and also among all of them resulted in significant differences in subjects' overall and differential test and task performances. In addition, regression analyses revealed that the greatest influence on subjects' overall and differential test and task performance was due to language proficiency. The implications of the study are discussed.

- 17** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2003). Text-familiarity, reading tasks and ESP test performance: A study on Iranian LEP and Non-LEP university students. *The Reading Matrix, 3*(1), online.

In a study of the effects of text familiarity, task type, and language proficiency on university students' LSP test and task performances (Salmani Nodoushan, 2003), 541 senior and junior university students majoring in electronics took the TBRT (Task-Based Reading Test). Variance analyses indicated that text familiarity, task type, and language proficiency, as well as the interaction between any given pair of these and also among all of them resulted in significant differences in subjects' overall and differential test and task performances. In addition, regression analyses revealed that the greatest influence on subjects' overall and differential test and task performance was due to language proficiency. The implications of the study are discussed.

- 18** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006). A sociopragmatic comparative study of ostensible invitations in English and Farsi. *Speech Communication*, 48(8), 903-912.

In their study in 1990, Clark and Isaacs identified five properties and seven defining features that distinguished between English ostensible and genuine invitations (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006). To see if Persian ostensible and genuine invitations could be distinguished by the same features and properties, the present study was carried out. Forty five field workers observed and reported 566 ostensible and 607 genuine invitations. In addition, 34 undergraduate students were interviewed and 68 ostensible and 68 genuine invitations were gathered. Forty one pairs of friends were also interviewed and afforded 41 ostensible invitations. The results of the data analysis revealed that Persian ostensible invitations can also be distinguished from Persian genuine invitations by the features and properties identified by Clark and Isaacs.

- 19** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006). Does field independence relate to performance on communicative language tests? *Journal of Educational Technology*, 3(3), 79-85.

Recent language testing research investigates factors other than language proficiency that may be responsible for systematic variance in language test performance (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006). One such factor is the test takers' cognitive styles. The present study was carried out with the aim of finding the probable effects of Iranian EFL learners' cognitive styles on their performance on communicative tests. For purposes of the present study, it was hypothesized that field (in)dependence would introduce systematic variance into Iranian EFL learners' communicative-test performance. 240 junior and senior students all majoring in English took the Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT), the 1990 version of IELTS, and the Communicative Test (CT) designed for the present study. The results of the present study provided evidence that the field-dependent (FD) subjects, compared to their field independent (FI) counterparts, performed much better on the CT. It was, therefore, concluded that test takers' cognitive styles may be viewed as a source of systematic variance in performance on communicative language tests.

- 20 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006). Greetings forms in English and Persian: A sociopragmatic perspective. *International Journal of Language, Culture, and Society*, 17. online.

In order to compare English and Persian greeting forms, Salmani Nodoushan (2006) used a model of sociopragmatic contrastive analysis. The corpus used for the study comprised of Persian greetings used in naturalistic contexts and English greetings used in movies and other video or audio media. The analyses revealed two patterns for English greetings and 5 patterns for Persian greetings. The results and pedagogical implications of the study are discussed.

- 21 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006). Language teaching: State of the art. *Asian EFL Journal*, 8(1), 169-193.

In its lifetime, the profession of language teaching has undergone many changes. Early attempts at language teaching almost entirely lacked a theoretical base. In the 20th century, however, two sets of language teaching methods emerged; the first set borrowed theories from psychology, linguistics, and sociolinguistics whereas the second set was based on individual philosophies of method developers. Late in the twentieth century, an attempt on the part of some pedagogists to evaluate the different methods of language teaching resulted in the validity of language teaching methods being called into question (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006). As a result, the question of how the profession of language pedagogy should be approached called into attention such notions as teacher plausibility, autonomy, and reflectivity as well as learner plausibility and autonomy. The result of such an expanded perspective was the introduction of effective and reflective teaching ideologies of the seventies and eighties. In 1994, an attempt at finding an alternative to methods instead of an alternative method culminated in the introduction of the post method era. The present paper tries to provide the reader with a brief account of these trends.

- 22 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006). Research in the language classroom: State of the art. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 3(2), 63-72.

Salmani Nodoushan (2006) argues that new trends in language teaching have resulted in a move towards research in the language classroom. A brief overview of classroom research reveals three distinct but inter-related research paradigms: classroom-centered research, classroom process research, and qualitative research, respectively.

- 23 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). A brief overview of classroom research. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(3), 367-374.

Salmani Nodoushan (2007) argues that new trends in language teaching have resulted in a move towards research in the language classroom. A brief overview of classroom research reveals three distinct but inter-related

research paradigms: classroom-centered research, classroom process research, and qualitative research, respectively.

- 24 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Are task type and text familiarity predictors of performance on tests of English for specific purposes? *Asian ESP Journal*, 3(1), 67-96.

In a study of the effects of text familiarity, task type, and language proficiency on university students' Language for Specific Purposes Ability (LSPA) test and task performances (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007), 541 senior and junior university students majoring in electronics took the Task-Based Reading Test (TBRT). Variance analyses indicated that text familiarity, task type, and language proficiency, as well as the interaction between any given pair of these and also among all of them resulted in significant differences in participants' overall and differential test and task performances. In addition, regression analyses revealed that the greatest influence on subjects' overall and differential test and task performances was due to language proficiency. Text familiarity had the smallest effect on students' test and task scores. Compared to text familiarity, task type was a stronger predictor of variance in test and task performance.

- 25 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Conversational strategies in Farsi complaints: The case of Iranian complainers. *PhiN: Philologie Netz*, 39, 20-37.

In a study of the effects of complainers' sex, age, perceived situational seriousness, and social class on the use of conversational strategies in their complaining behavior (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007), 465 subjects of varying age, sex, and social class were observed and tape recorded in spontaneous conversation by 25 field workers. The field workers also filled out a checklist that provided the data of the study, which were then input into two nonparametric tests: (a) Mann-Whitney U Test, and (b) Kruskal Wallis H Test. The results of data analysis showed that 'repetition of complaint' was an important strategy in connection to the 'perceived situational seriousness' of the topic of complaint. Sex was found to cause the differential use of three conversational strategies, social class to cause the differential use of two conversational strategies, and perceived situational seriousness and age each to cause that of only on conversational strategy. A cline of significance is suggested for each of the independent variables in question. Suggestions are made for further research.

- 26 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Error treatment in the EFL writing class: Red pen method versus remedial instruction. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 4(3), 53-58.

In a study by Salmani Nodoushan (2007) conducted to see which method of error treatment was more effective in EFL writing classes, 288 Iranian EFL learners took the TOEFL test to be grouped in two homogeneous classes. Each student in each group wrote a paragraph on a general topic which was proofread for mistakes/errors by three experienced EFL writing teachers (i.e., Pretest). One group received Red Pen treatment (RPM) and the other Remedial Instruction treatment (RIM). After a two-week interval,

both groups repeated the same writing assignment proofread by the same teachers (Post-test). A Mixed Between-Within Subjects Analysis of Variance (SPANOVA) was conducted to analyze the effect of two different types of treatment (i.e., RPM, and RIM). Results, after analysis of the data, indicated that the main effect was significant for time but not for group. It was further noticed that the interaction effect was also significant. The RPM method, although not statistically significant, was slightly more effective in enhancing EFL written performance than the RIM method.

- 27 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Iranian complainers' use of conversational strategies: A politeness study. *Iranian Journal of Language Studies*, 1(1), 29-56.

In Salmani Nodoushan's (2007) study of the effects of complainers' sex, age, perceived situational seriousness, and social class on the use of conversational strategies in their response to complaining behavior of complainers, 465 subjects of varying age, sex, and social class were observed and tape recorded in spontaneous conversation by 25 field workers. The field workers also filled out a checklist that provided the data of the study, which were then input into two nonparametric tests: (a) Mann-Whitney U Test, and (b) Kruskal Wallis H Test. The results of data analysis showed that sex and social class caused the differential use of two conversational strategies whereas perceived situational seriousness caused the differential use of only one strategy. The results also indicated that age resulted in the differential use of none of the conversational strategies in questions.

- 28 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Is cognitive style a precursor to EFL reading performance? *Journal on Educational Technology*, 4(1), 66-86.

In Salmani Nodoushan's (2007) study, it was hypothesized that field dependence or independence would introduce systematic variance into Iranian EFL learners' overall and task-specific performance on task-based reading comprehension tests. One thousand, seven hundred, forty-three freshman, sophomore, junior, and senior students, all majoring in English at various Iranian universities and colleges, took the Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT). The resulting 582 field-independent (FI) and 707 field-dependent (FD) students then took the 1990 version of the IELTS. Using SPSS commands for collapsing continuous variables into groups and participants' IELTS scores (based on the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles), four proficiency groups were identified for each cognitive style. From each proficiency group, 36 FD and 36 FI individuals were selected through a matching process. The resulting sample of 288 participants took the Task-Based Reading Test (TBRT) designed for the study. Data analysis revealed that individuals' cognitive styles resulted in a significant difference in their overall test performance in the proficient, semiproficient, and fairly proficient groups, but not in the low-proficient group. The findings also indicated that cognitive style resulted in a significant difference in participants' performance on true-false, sentence completion, outlining, scanning, and elicitation tasks in all proficiency groups.

- 29 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Is field dependence or independence a predictor of EFL reading performance? *TESL Canada Journal*, 24(2), 82-108.

In Salmani Nodoushan's (2007) study, it was hypothesized that field dependence or independence would introduce systematic variance into Iranian EFL learners' overall and task-specific performance on task-based reading comprehension tests. One thousand, seven hundred, forty-three freshman, sophomore, junior, and senior students, all majoring in English at various Iranian universities and colleges, took the Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT). The resulting 582 field-independent (FI) and 707 field-dependent (FD) students then took the 1990 version of the IELTS. Using SPSS commands for collapsing continuous variables into groups and participants' IELTS scores (based on the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles), four proficiency groups were identified for each cognitive style. From each proficiency group, 36 FD and 36 FI individuals were selected through a matching process. The resulting sample of 288 participants took the Task-Based Reading Test (TBRT) designed for the study. Data analysis revealed that individuals' cognitive styles resulted in a significant difference in their overall test performance in the proficient, semiproficient, and fairly proficient groups, but not in the low-proficient group. The findings also indicated that cognitive style resulted in a significant difference in participants' performance on true-false, sentence completion, outlining, scanning, and elicitation tasks in all proficiency groups.

- 30 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Is text cohesion a precursor to reading success? *Journal of Educational Technology*, 3(4), 87-91.

This study by Salmani Nodoushan (2007) underscores the effect of text cohesion on EFL reading comprehension. 160 EFL (n=80) and non-EFL (n=80) university students took two versions of a cloze test based on a passage of 750 words length, one developed with every nth word deletion and the other with cohesive word deletion. The results of analyses of variance indicated that text cohesion positively affected text comprehension. Pedagogical implications of the study are discussed.

- 31 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). On adopting a cognitive orientation in EFL writing classroom. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 1(1), 15-18.

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2007) underscores the importance of the cognitive orientation of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students in their success in writing courses. A few suggestions are made as to how EFL teachers can put their students on the right cognitive path in their writings.

- 32 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Politeness markers in Persian requestives. *The Linguistics Journal*, 2(1), 43-68.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2007) aims at finding out whether Arabic learners of English (Emarati Females in particular) produce target-like compliment responses in English and whether pragmatic transfer can occur. Discourse completion tests (DCTs) and interviews were used to

study the strategies employed when responding to compliments by native speakers (NSs) and Arabic non-native speakers (NNSs) of English. Findings suggest that Arabic (L1) expressions and strategies were sometimes transferred to English (L2). This study also indicates that Emarati female learners of English transfer some of their L1 pragmatic norms to L2 because they perceive these norms to be universal among languages rather than being language specific. It also indicates that Arabic NNSs of English have some misconceptions about NSs that affect the way they respond to their compliments. Some important cultural and pedagogical implications are discussed at the end of the paper.

- 33** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Thinking on the write path. *Training Journal*, May 2007, 37-40.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2007) paper emphasizes the importance of cognitive orientation to the success of EFL students in writing courses. It argues that the skill of writing was rediscovered as soon as it lost its lowly status as a 'by-product' of the oral approach. In this paper, inefficient writing is attributed to a number of factors, among which the inadequacy of cognitive competence stands out. It suggest a cognitive approach to teaching writing the aim of which is to develop an insight in the learner, enabling him to make his own selections and interpretations of the existing situation. The main component of instruction in a cognitive approach is revision. As they take on the role of both writers and readers, the students are taught to review their writing, predicting what problems they may have, and what possible reactions they may have to their writing. The suggestion here is to write some of the compositions on the board or to use an overhead/opaque projector to this end. The students may then be urged to identify the mistakes, both grammatical and rhetorical, in their compositions. This procedure can develop an interactional attitude, and enhance productive thinking in the students.

- 34** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). A critique of the brave new world of K-12 education. *Journal on School Educational Technology*, 4(2), 1-6.

Salmani Nodoushan (2008) argues that the rapid development of transportation systems and communication technology, and the growth of population has resulted in the appearance of new settlements even in such remote areas of Earth as rain forests and deserts. This has stimulated the need for a replacement for traditional education systems. K-12 education has emerged from the no-child-left-behind concerns of governments for educating the young population of their countries. This paper is a critique of such an educational system. It begins with a definition of K-12 distance education, and notices the five most popular K-12 systems: Statewide supplemental programs, District-level supplemental programs, Single-district cyber schools, Multi-district cyber schools, and Cyber charters. It then describes the most popular instructional practices within these K-12 systems and identifies them as: Instructor-led Training (ILT), Collaborative Learning, Computer-based Training (CBT), Web-based Training (WBT),

and Electronic Performance Support System (EPSS). Then the paper compares K-12 education to traditional educational systems and identifies their advantages and disadvantages. In the end it concludes that computer or mass media technology has no special powers to enhance and facilitate learning unless it is embedded with instruction that addresses social and cognitive processes of knowledge construction.

- 35 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). A framework for task-oriented language instruction. *Journal on School Educational Technology*, 3(3), 5-16.

According to the paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2008), task-based teaching is an area which has emerged from the upsurge of interest in cognitive approaches to language learning and teaching of the mid 1980s. Being a current vogue in communicative language teaching, task-based language learning contains dangers if implemented without care. In particular, it is likely to create pressure for immediate communication rather than interlanguage change and growth. In this process, it may persuade learners to use lexical modes of communication excessively and prematurely, and to fossilize some way short of native-like second language competence. This paper takes a processing-pedagogic viewpoint to review what task-based instruction is, to identify its goals, and to warn EFL/ESL teachers about the potential pitfalls of task-based language teaching.

- 36 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). Conversational strategies in Farsi complaints: The case of Iranian complainers. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 2(2), 187-214.

In the study of the effects of complainers' sex, age, perceived situational seriousness, and social class on the use of conversational strategies in their response to complaining behavior of complainers by Salmani Nodoushan (2008), 465 subjects of varying age, sex, and social class were observed and tape recorded in spontaneous conversation by 25 field workers. The field workers also filled out a checklist that provided the data of the study, which were then input into two nonparametric tests: (a) Mann-Whitney U Test, and (b) Kruskal Wallis H Test. The results of data analysis showed that sex and social class caused the differential use of two conversational strategies whereas perceived situational seriousness caused the differential use of only one strategy. The results also indicated that age resulted in the differential use of none of the conversational strategies in questions.

- 37 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). Language and literacy development in prelingually-deaf children. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 2(2), 16-20.

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2008) attempts to address the issue of language development in hearing impaired children. It argues that interpreters, teachers or peers can provide deaf children with language exposure so that they can acquire their native languages more easily. It also argues that the provision of a developmentally appropriate print-rich environments is the key to literacy success and that providing deaf students with the opportunity to respond to and ask questions in the classroom will

help them acquire language. It is noted that if peers learn to sign, and if teachers teach them to sign, it will increase the opportunity for social interaction for deaf students whereby affecting their learning outcomes. It stresses the point that the presence of deaf students in a class should be a learning experience for everyone. It also discusses strategies that can be incorporated into teaching by teachers for helping children with hearing impairments achieve more.

- 38** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). Performance assessment in language testing. *Journal on School Educational Technology*, 3(4), 1-7.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2008), over the past few decades, educators in general, and language teachers in specific, were more inclined towards using testing techniques that resembled real life-language performance. Unlike traditional paper-and-pencil language tests that required test-takers to attempt tests that were based on artificial and contrived language content, performance tests are authentic so that the test-taker is asked to perform language tasks that he or she will need to perform in real-life interactions. A very valuable type of performance test is called portfolio assessment in which a record of students' performance across a wide range of language tasks over a logical period of time is kept so that a profile of performance can be obtained for the evaluation of achievement. This paper will define performance assessment, trace its origins and development, explain how performance tests can be constructed, and describes the nature and advantages of portfolios.

- 39** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). Persian requests: Redress of face through indirectness. *Iranian Journal of Language Studies*, 2(3), 257-280.

Salmani Nodoushan (2008) reports the findings of a study designed to investigate the notion of indirectness in the speech act of requests among native speakers of Persian across different levels of Perceived Situational Seriousness. 372 respondents took a Discourse Completion Test (DCT) with six scenarios ranging from formal to informal degrees of Perceived Situational Seriousness (PSS), and returned 2232 Requestive Speech Acts (RSAs). The acts were then analyzed according to models proposed by Blum-Kulka, et al. (1989), and Scollon and Scollon (2001). Results, after analysis of the data, indicated that, in general, native speakers of Persian prefer conventionally indirect (CI) strategies when issuing requests. Social distance was found to trigger indirectness in requestive speech acts (RSAs); solidarity was found to enhance addressors' inclination towards directness in RSAs. It was further noticed that pragmatic knowledge (i.e., knowledge of the world and of each other that interlocutors share) resulted in Persian native speakers' inclination towards NCI strategies in RSAs.

- 40** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). The quantum human computer (QHC) hypothesis. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 4(4), 28-32.

The article by Salmani Nodoushan (2008) attempts to suggest the existence of a human computer called Quantum Human Computer (QHC) on the

basis of an analogy between human beings and computers. To date, there are two types of computers: Binary and Quantum. The former operates on the basis of binary logic where an object is said to exist in either of the two states of 1 and 0. The latter, however, operates on the basis of fuzzy logic where an object can exist in more than two states simultaneously. Through analogy, it is hypothesized that human beings are superb quantum computers that operate on the basis of human logic that accepts multiple states for objects simultaneously. Moreover, and since human beings are composed of physique, mind, memory, soul, and spirit, it is also hypothesized that the QHC legalizes the existence of objects in Hilbert space. Finally, it is further suggested that, as fictitious as it may seem, human learning can be reduced into a "suggestion model" whereby information is suggested into the human computer in much the same way as a given software is setup on a digital computer; the paper proposes a model for human learning based on its description of the quantum human computer. It is claimed that human learning can be whole sale rather than being linear, sequential and time-consuming. Sleep and hypnosis are presented as examples.

- 41 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). The role of metacognition in the language teaching profession. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 2(1), 1-9.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2008), metacognition is a concept in psychology that refers to a variety of self-awareness process that help learners learn better. It grew out of the developments over the past few decades of cognitive models of learning. This paper will present a brief overview of these models and discuss their main features. It begins with a discussion of behavioristic models of learning, will go on with a discussion of cognitive learning models and will end in an elaboration of constructivist, humanistic and social interactionist models of human learning. It will then link these learning models to language learning and discuss how they can be applied to help language learners achieve language competence.

- 42 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Identifying sources of bias in EFL writing assessment through multiple trait scoring. *The Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1(2), 28-53.

For purposes of the study by Salmani Nodoushan (2009), it was hypothesized that field (in) dependence would introduce systematic variance into EFL learners' performance on composition tests. 1743 freshman, sophomore, junior, and senior students all majoring in English at different Iranian universities and colleges took the Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT). The resulting 582 Field-Independent (FI) and the 707 Field-Dependent (FD) students then took the 2000 version of the IELTS. Using SPSS commands for collapsing continuous variables into groups, and participants' IELTS scores (based on 25, 50, 75 percentiles), four proficiency groups were identified for each kind of cognitive styles. From each proficiency group, 36 FD and 36 FI individuals were selected through

a matching process. The scores obtained by the resulting sample of 288 participants on the second writing task of the IELTS test were used as the data for this study. The results of data analysis revealed that individuals' cognitive styles resulted in a significant difference in their writing performance in proficient, semi-proficient, and fairly proficient groups, but not in the low proficient group. The findings also indicated that cognitive style resulted in a significant difference in participants' performance on such aspects of EFL composition as content, structure, and language.

- 43 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Improving learning and teaching through action research. *The Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1(4), 211-222.

In this paper, Salmani Nodoushan (2009) has argued that action research, unlike traditional forms of qualitative and quantitative research, focuses only on classroom problems that require informed decisions and solutions. Action research is conducted in seven simple steps. It is distinguished from other research forms in terms of scope, sample size, data types, and data analysis techniques. Many teachers and administrators find action research a very practical and user-friendly approach to conducting research since it is less formal than traditional research types.

- 44 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Is EFL study major a predictor of language achievement. *The Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1(3), 182-193.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2009) study intended to see if, everything else being equal, participants' study major really affected their language achievement. It was hypothesized that the exact EFL sub-discipline (i.e., Translation, Literature, or Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL)) in which students are majoring affects their language achievement in meaningful ways. A total of 198 (N=198) university students all majoring in English took their ordinary courses and at the end of the semester, they were given their exams. Their semester-end cumulative grade point averages (GPA) were compared to their previous-term GPAs. SPANOVA results did not identify study major to be a predictor of language achievement.

- 45 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Measurement theory in language testing: Past traditions and current trends. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 3(2), 1-12.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2009), a good test is one that has at least three qualities: reliability, or the precision with which a test measures what it is supposed to measure; validity, i.e., if the test really measures what it is supposed to measure, and practicality, or if the test, no matter how sound theoretically, is practicable in reality. These are the sine qua non for any test including tests of language proficiency. Over the past fifty years, language testing has witnessed three major measurement trends: Classical Test Theory (CTT), Generalizability Theory (G-Theory), and Item Response Theory (IRT). This paper will provide a very brief but valuable overview of these trends. It will then move onto a brief consideration of the most recent notion of Differential Item Functioning (DIF). It will finally

conclude that the material discussed here is applicable not only to language tests but also to tests in other fields of science.

- 46 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Morphological make-up as the predictor of English word accent. *TESL Canada Journal*, 26(2), 13-23.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2009), for years, phoneticians have tried to simplify pronunciation for EFL/ESL learners. Some have identified four degrees of primary, secondary, tertiary, and weak stress, and others only three degrees: primary, secondary, and weak. Still others have concentrated on two stress levels: accented versus unaccented, or stressed versus unstressed (Bowen, 1975; Stageberg, 1964; Chomsky & Halle, 1968). None, however, has followed an orthography-based approach to English accent. Because orthography is the most static way of representing words in English, spelling- or orthography-based rules of accent/stress placement may come as a relief to ESL/EFL learners. In this article I present four spelling-based rules for stress placement to help EFL/ESL learners master pronunciation.

- 47 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). The Shaffer-Gee perspective: Can epistemic games serve education? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(6), 897-901.

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2009) addresses the issue of how games can reshape education by describing current educational practices. It argues that there are conservative camps that emphasize structure and development of basic literacy and numeracy skills in education as well as liberal camps that emphasize immersion, and notices that both camps fail to train students able to address the crisis of innovation. A post-progressive pedagogy that integrates both structure and immersion to address this innovation crisis is described in the paper. It is also emphasized that epistemic games can serve as excellent tools at the hand of this post-progressive pedagogy.

- 48 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). *A primer of phonetics*. Raleigh, NC: Lulu Press Inc.

A primer of phonetics (Salmani Nodoushan, 2010) is designed to support EFL learners in achieving native-like pronunciation: Chapter one deals with the history of phonology and phonetics and provides a brief overview of the impact of philosophy and psychology on the emergence of phonology. Chapter two defines the notion of phoneme, describes IPA phonetic alphabet, and distinguishes between broad and narrow transcriptions. Chapters three and four provide an in-depth account of traditional and systematic articulatory phonetics respectively. Chapter five discusses the place of suprasegmentals in phonology. Chapter six seeks to explain phonemics. Chapter seven provides a brief introduction to the rudiments of acoustic or physical phonetics. Chapter eight introduces the reader to the notion of auditory phonetics. The tables, figures, and photos that are presented throughout the book are designed to give the reader an instant reference for the precise articulation of English phonemes.

- 49 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). Review of the book An introduction to phonetics & phonology by J. Clark & C. Yallop. *Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 2(3), 249-251.

In this book review, Salmani Nodoushan (2010) argues that, assuming no prior knowledge of the subject, this book offers a thorough introduction to phonetics and phonology. It is unusually comprehensive, including detailed attention to articulatory and acoustic phonetics as well as to the foundations of phonological analysis. The second edition of this highly successful textbook incorporates several improvements: a completely new chapter on speech perception has been added, the material on anatomy and physiology has been rearranged and much of the detail placed later in the book to make it less demanding on readers, and the entire text has been edited to help bring it up to date.

- 50 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). The impact of formal schemata on L3 reading recall. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 4(4), 113-128.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2010), Rhetorical structure refers to a complex network of relationships and the way the underlying ideas are organized within a text. This study was conducted to see whether explicit instruction of descriptive and causative text organization positively affected L3 reading recall. 240 Turkish students of EFL who had Persian as their second language were assigned to two groups (experimental and control) controlled for language proficiency with only the former receiving instruction in rhetorical organization. Comparison of pre-test and post-test written recall data showed that explicit instruction had a positive effect on L3 reading recall. It was also noted that the amount of L3 reading recall was a function of the type of rhetorical organization of reading texts.

- 51 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). The Interface between interim assessment and feedback: An opinion paper. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 4(3), 1-8.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2010), many schools and educators prefer to use state tests. However, teachers can benefit a lot from the tests and quizzes they give in their classes over the course of a term or year. The minimum such tests can do is to afford information that teachers can use to assess how their class is learning and which changes in instruction need to be made to assure maximum outcome. This is a diagnostic quality that teacher-made tests possess, a quality that can technically be termed formative assessment which can be contrasted with summative assessment or making judgments about class achievement. This paper elaborates on the advantages of formative assessment and gives some examples to support teachers' use of it.

- 52 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). The silent disarmers: What L1 habits do to FL success. *Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 2(2), 187-189.

In this short forum, Salmani Nodoushan (2010) talks about What L1 habits do to FL success.

- 53 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). *Writing research reports: A guide for graduate students*. Raleigh, NC: Lulu Press Inc.

Salmani Nodoushan (2010) has designed the book *Writing research reports: A guide for graduate students* to foster in undergraduate students the skills they need for success in their research courses. The book consists of three distinct sections: APA style, Library Research, and Reports and Theses.

- 54 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). A structural move analysis of discussion sub-genre in applied linguistics. *6th International Conference on Languages, E-Learning and Romanian Studies*, Lund University, June 3-5, 2011, Marstrand, Sweden.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2011) aimed at finding the probable differences between the move structure of Iranian MA graduates' thesis discussion subgenres and those of their non-Iranian counterparts, on the one hand, and those of journal paper authors, on the other. It also aimed at identifying the moves that are considered obligatory, conventional, or optional by Iranian MA graduates. 46 (N = 46) masters thesis 'discussion' sections taken randomly from a pool of 93 discussions written in English by Iranian EFL students comprised the corpus for this study. The AntMover software as well as two human coders identified and coded the moves found in the corpus. The resulting move frequencies were compared to those of Rasmeenin's (2006) study as well as Yang and Allison's (2003) framework using a set of Mann-Whitney U tests as well as One-Sample t-Tests. Results indicated that there is a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian versus non-Iranian EFL students. There was also a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian EFL students and the discussion sub-genre of journal papers published in internationally recognized applied-linguistic journals. Obligatory, conventional, and optional moves were also identified. It was concluded that academic writing teachers need to focus on move structures and make their students move-sensitive.

- 55 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). *Reading for the IELTS*. Raleigh, NC: Lulu Press Inc.

Reading for the IELTS by Salmani Nodoushan (2011) is a book that is intended to prepare its readers for taking the IELTS test. The fifteen units in the book have all been controlled for readability and difficulty so that maximum compatibility with the IELTS test developed by UCLES (University of Cambridge) will be maintained.

- 56 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). Reflective teaching in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes: An overview. *Journal on School Educational Technology*, 6(3), 1-6.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2011), since the beginning of the 20 century, professionals in language teaching have strived for ways that could guarantee better outcomes in language teaching classes. Different methods were used mostly in the first half of that century. Then some language teaching

professionals moved beyond methods with the hope of gaining greater results. In one case, some language teachers moved towards what is now called reflective teaching (RT). RT requires teachers' self-observation as well self-evaluation which should go on in a cyclical manner to ensure teachers' understanding of their own classroom actions so that refinements can be introduced where necessary. RT is a process whereby teachers' reflect on their own classroom actions to collect and analyze descriptive data which can show where a change for better can be made. RT results in teacher and material flexibility and teacher professionalism. This paper provides a descriptive account of RT in language classrooms.

- 57 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). Temperament as an indicator of language achievement. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 5(4), 33-52.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2011), language learning is a complex process that is controlled or influenced by a host of linguistic and non-linguistic factors. Some of these factors are the main concerns of psychologists rather than linguists. Ever since psychology began to develop in the 20th century, more and more individual characteristics were identified and defined. Eysenck's introduction of a way to measure temperament interested (applied) linguists, and some of them tried to investigate the influence of temperament on language learning. The present study, too, set out to investigate the probable effects of temperament on EFL speaking achievement. 139 Iranian intermediate-proficiency university students took the U-test, an IELTS-based structured interview, and the Eysenck Personality Test. They then took a speaking course. Another structured interview was conducted at the end of the course as the post-test. The results of a Mixed between-within Subjects Analysis of Variance (SPANOVA) indicated that introverts were advantaged in speaking achievement. The sanguine participants in the study outperformed the choleric ones who in turn outperformed the melancholic participants. The weakest results belonged to the phlegmatic participant group.

- 58 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). The place of genre analysis in international communication. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 5(1), 63-74.

According to Salmani Nodoushan (2011), writing is most probably the most difficult skill for ESL/EFL learners to master. It is difficult not only because it requires junior writers to generate and organize ideas in a language other than their mother tongue but also because it forces them to present their already generated and organized ideas in such a text form that is understandable to readers from a wide range of socio-cultural backgrounds as well as to the native speakers of English. Therefore, the question of how to teach writing in a second/foreign language has been at the center of attention for a good number of researchers and educators over the past decades. Attempts at determining how to teach writing, and what to teach in writing courses, have resulted in the development of teaching methods, materials, and procedures which are based on an analysis of different genres, and the quest is still going on. This paper provides a brief overview of genre analysis, discusses the notions of Genre Constellations, Genre hierarchies, Genre chains, Genre Sets, Genre Networks,

and Subgenres, and elaborates on the relationship of genre analysis to international communication.

- 59** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2012). A structural move analysis of discussion sub-genre in applied linguistics. *DacoRomania*, 17(2), 199-212.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2012), aimed at finding the probable differences between the move structure of Iranian MA graduates' thesis discussion subgenres and those of their non-Iranian counterparts, on the one hand, and those of journal paper authors, on the other. It also aimed at identifying the moves that are considered obligatory, conventional, or optional by Iranian MA graduates. 46 (N = 46) master's thesis 'discussion' sections taken randomly from a pool of 93 discussions written in English by Iranian EFL students comprised the corpus for this study. The AntMover software as well as two human coders identified and coded the moves found in the corpus. The resulting move frequencies were compared to those of Rasmeenin's (2006) study as well as Yang and Allison's (2003) framework using a set of Mann-Whitney U tests as well as One-Sample t-Tests. Results indicated that there is a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian versus non-Iranian EFL students. There was also a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian EFL students and the discussion sub-genre of journal papers published in internationally recognized applied-linguistic journals. Obligatory, conventional, and optional moves were also identified. It was concluded that academic writing teachers need to focus on move structures and make their students move-sensitive.

- 60** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2012). Rethinking face and politeness. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 6(4), 119-140.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2012), addresses the concepts of face and (im)politeness from both first-order and second-order perspectives, and attempts at rethinking face, (im)politeness, and Face-Threatening Acts (FTAs). It suggests that each and every speech act is issued as a result of the interplay between self's intention and his motivation, with intention being the ignition, and motivation the fuel. Listing a number of features of speech acts, the paper further argues that FTAs must be redefined, and suggests the existence of Face-Attacking Acts (FAAs) as well as Face-Guarding Acts (FGAs)—but uses FAAs as a cover term for both. The paper also suggests a model for the description of FAAs/FGAs, and argues that they fall into four classes: (1) self-destructive hypothetical FAAs, (2) self-/other-guarding hypothetical FGAs, (3) other-destructive objective FAAs, and (4) self-/other-guarding objective FGAs. It then goes on to rethink the concept of (im)politeness, and suggests a model for politeness theory which entails a redefinition of politeness and impoliteness. It provides colorful examples and tangible evidence to relate (im)politeness to both context and collective pragmatic competence, and claims that action can be dominant or recess to speech just like dominant versus recess genes in biology.

- 61 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2012). Self-regulated learning (SRL): Emergence of the RSRLM model. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 6(3), 1-16.

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2012), claims that the current theories of Self-regulated learning (SRL) are short-sighted. The author provides a comprehensive, but brief, overview of SRL which addresses such issues as (a) SRL processes, (b) SRL strategies, (c) compartments of SRL, (d) theories of SRL, (e) agency in SRL, and (f) models of SRL. He then presents a new model for SRL (namely, the Revised Self-Regulated Learning Model (RSRLM)), and focuses on the role of dyadic agency in SRL. The paper concludes that SRL models need to take into account the roles played by social support systems.

- 62 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2012). The impact of locus of control on language achievement. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 6(2), 123-136.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2012), hypothesized that students' loci of control affected their language achievement. 198 (N=198) EFL students took the Rotter's (1966) locus of control test and were classified as locus-internal (ni=78), and locus-external (ne=120). They then took their ordinary courses and at the end of the semester, they were given their exams. Their semester-end cumulative grade point averages (GPA) were compared to their previous-term GPA. SPANOVA results did not identify locus of control (LoC) as a predictor of achievement. Results also indicated that factors like LoC, if at all, interact with proficiency only at the advanced level.

- 63 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2013). Review of the book *Philosophical perspectives for pragmatics* by M. Sbisà, J. O. Östman & J. Verschueren. *Linguistik Online*, 58(1), 119-126.

This work is a book review by Salmani Nodoushan (2013): Review of the book *Philosophical perspectives for pragmatics* by M. Sbisà, J. O. Östman & J. Verschueren. Amsterdam/Philadelphia.: John Benjamins. (= Handbook of Pragmatic 10).

- 64 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2013). The bilingual self or selves? *Annals Universitatis Apulensis - Series Philologica*, 14(2), 503-510.

In a study by Salmani Nodoushan (2013), a concise but strong review of the literature on bilinguals' perception of 'self' led to the question of whether bilinguals perceive themselves as different or the same people when they function in different languages. 183 participants (N =183) randomly assigned to two half-groups took both the English and Persian versions of the Self Concept Scale (SCS) in two counter-balanced administration sessions with a time interval of 3 weeks. Results after analysis of the data using descriptive and inferential statistics indicated that Iranian-Americans have a more realistic self-concept when they function in English than when they function in Persian. Their self-concepts in English and Persian do not match. Moreover, the female Iranian-American shows a larger discrepancy in her English and Persian self-concepts than her male counterpart. This indicates that females are more open to alienation than males are. The results of this study lend empirical support to

claims made by previous researchers that bilinguals have a kind of split personality. It was concluded that a bilingual is not a unique person who assumes different identities when he functions in the different languages he knows, but that the bilingual possess two different guises or selves which are language-specific and are used in accordance with the language the bilingual speaks at any given point in time.

- 65** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2013). The social semiotics of funerary rites in Iran. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 7(1), 79-102.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2013) argues that speech acts find occasion in two different contexts: (a) interpersonal, and (b) social. While the aim of speech acts produced in the former context is to create a communicative effect, the speech acts produced in the latter context aim at creating a social effect. Building on a seminal work done by Capone (2010), this study addressed funerary rites in the Shiite population of Iran. This paper reports the results of the study and classifies the speech acts produced in Shia funerary rites into three classes of speech: (a) language addressed to Allah, (b) language addressed to the deceased, and (c) language addressed to the grieved relatives of the deceased. Samples of speech in any of these situations are provided and analyzed within the framework of conventional speech acts and pragmemes. Comparing Shia funerary rites and Catholic death rituals, the paper concludes that funerary rites function on two planes: (a) the psychological plane that aims at providing solace for the grieved relatives of the deceased, and (b) the social plane that aims at enhancing collective social intentionality.

- 66** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). Assessing writing: A review of the main trends. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 1(2), 119-129.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2014) argues that as a language skill, writing has had, still has and will continue have an important role in shaping the scientific structure of human life in that it is the medium through which scientific content is stored, retained, and transmitted. It has therefore been a major concern for writing teachers and researchers to find a reliable method for evaluating and ensuring quality writing. This paper addresses the different approaches to scoring writing and classifies them into a priori scoring systems (including holistic and analytic scoring), and a posteriori scoring systems (including primary-trait and multiple-trait scoring).

- 67** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). Cognitive versus learning styles: Emergence of the Ideal Education Model (IEM). *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 8(2), 31-39.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2014) argues that societies have strived through centuries to develop educational systems that would foster the most idealistic educational outcomes in learners. The recurring patterns of underachievement and the growing rates of student drop-outs resulted in psychologists' and educators' attempts at a pathological examination of the causes of student failure. Models of learning and cognitive styles were proposed as possible explanation. This paper briefly reviews some of the most influential models and draws readers' attention to their inherent shortcomings.

It then proposes a more comprehensive model—the Ideal Education Model (IEM).

- 68** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). Review of the book *Perspectives on pragmatics and philosophy* by A. Capone, F. Lo Piparo & M. Carapezza. *Intercultural Pragmatics*, *11*(2), 301-306. (DOI: DOI 10.1515/ip-2014-0013)

This work is a book review by Salmani Nodoushan (2014): Review of Capone, Alessandro, Franco Lo Piparo, & Marco Carapezza (eds.). 2013. *Perspectives in Pragmatics, Philosophy & Psychology (Volume 1): Perspectives on Pragmatics and Philosophy*. Heidelberg: Springer International Publishing [647 pp. ISBN 978-3-319-01010-6].

- 69** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). Review of the book *Perspectives on linguistic pragmatics* by A. Capone, F. Lo Piparo & M. Carapezza. *Intercultural Pragmatics*, *11*(4), 645-649. (DOI: 10.1515/ip-2014-0028)

This work is a book review by Salmani Nodoushan (2014): Review of Capone, A., Lo Piparo, F., & Carapezza, M. (eds.). (2013). *Perspectives in Pragmatics, Philosophy & Psychology, Volume 2: Perspectives on Linguistic Pragmatics*. Springer International Publishing. [xxv + 542 pp; ISBN: 978-3-319-01013-7]

- 70** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). Speech acts or language micro- and macro-games? *International Journal of Language Studies*, *8*(4), 1-28.

In this paper, Salmani Nodoushan (2014) begins with a description of the origins of the speech act theory, and the classifications of speech acts. Then, he reviews different camps of thought which had a bearing on our current understanding of speech acts, and specifically focus on Halliday's metafunctions, Isaacs and Clark's ostensible and genuine acts, Sperber and Wilson's relevance theory, Mey's conception of pragmemes, and Wittgenstein's concept of language games. He then puts these together in my general discussion to present my own view of speech acts which he sees as language micro- and macro-games. In my discussion of my own views, he suggests that any act of language use (be it semiotic, kinesthetic, proxemic, verbal, orthographical, or otherwise) is essentially a language micro- or macro-game. Finally, he describes his own model of 'language game constellations' which comprises language game sets, hierarchies, chains, and networks.

- 71** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Anxiety as it pertains to EFL writing ability and performance. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, *8*(4), 1-12.

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2015) reports the results of a study conducted to find (a) the impact of anxiety on EFL learners' writing performance, and (b) the relationship between anxiety and foreign language writing ability. 137 (N = 137) EFL learners took the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), the Oxford Placement Test (OPT), and a writing task on a sensitive political topic. Results of the FLCAS were used to assess the participants' degrees of trait, state, and situational anxiety, and OPT scores indicated their proficiency levels. The writing task scores were used as a measure for the participants' writing task performance. Regression and

partial correlation analyses were conducted. The findings of the study showed that state anxiety is debilitating whereas situational anxiety and trait anxiety are facilitative. It was concluded that mitigation strategies, discursive textual techniques, and the use of passive voice are in fact triggered by state anxiety rather than by writers' face-saving intentions or their inclination to show politeness.

- 72 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Review of the book *An Anthropology of Learning: On Nested Frictions in Cultural Ecologies* by C. Hasse. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(6), E30-E31.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2015) book review: This book combines cultural models with practice-based learning to develop a new theory of cultural learning. Drawing on insights from anthropology, it argues how collective and social cultures can emerge from an 'engaged' learning process. The book opens another window on human learning, so you will probably find only parts of the text of some interest or use.

- 73 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Review of the book *Cognitive coaching* by J. Ellison & C. Hayes. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(5), E21-E22.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2015) book review: Presupposing that the principles of Cognitive CoachingSM have the potential to transform individuals' identities, this edited volume claims that the same principles can also transform the identities of organisations. However, if you already know the principles of Cognitive Coaching, you will probably find only parts of the text of some interest or use.

- 74 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Review of the book *Intercultural pragmatics* by I. Kecskes. *Pragmatics & Society*, 6(1), 152–156. doi 10.1075/ps.6.1.08nod

Salmani Nodoushan's (2015) book review: Review of Kecskes, Istvan. 2013. *Intercultural Pragmatics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. [vii + 277 pp; ISBN: 978-0-19-989265-5]

- 75 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Review of the book *Networked Learning: An Educational Paradigm for the Age of Digital Networks* by C. Jones. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(6), E31-E32.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2015) book review: This book is largely about how people connect with each other and with digital technologies, and how this affects their learning. It reviews existing literature on networked learning and describes the role of universities and academics in networked learning. The book targets anyone interested in learning technologies, so I recommend that you arrange to borrow a copy for a while.

- 76 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Review of the book *Teaching for creativity in the common core classroom* by R. A. Beghetto, J. C. Kaufman & J. Baer. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(5), E21-E22.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2015) book review: Targeting classroom teachers working to the US Common Core standards, this book draws on cutting-edge

psychological research to show the intricate interface between that approach and teaching for creativity, perhaps an opposite. It presents remarkable practical advice on how restricted curriculum classroom teachers can foster creativity in the learners. If—but only if—you are a Common Core classroom teacher, I recommend that you buy a copy of this book for your own use. Otherwise, if the content of this book is still likely to be relevant to you, you will probably find parts of it of interest or use.

- 77** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Review of the book *Ways of learning: Learning theories and learning styles in the classroom* by A. Pritchard. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(6), E34-E35.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2015) book review: Written for teachers, who generally lack a sufficient knowledge of how people learn, Pritchard's book aims at enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of education through raising teachers' understanding of learning theory. However, it does not do so very effectively: even if you are a keen teacher, you will probably find only parts of much interest or use.

- 78** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). The secret life of slurs from the perspective of reported speech. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 9(2), 92-112.

Research on reported speech is old, but scholars working in this field are inclined to see its roots in Davidson's (1968) paratactic account of indirect reports. Although Davidson aimed at a 'truth-conditional' theory of indirect reports which could challenge ideational, use, and psychological theories, his paratactic view – of which the backbone was the notion of 'samesaying' – motivated a good number of scholars to search for adequate accounts of indirect reports in truth-conditional semantics. Ever since then, research on reported speech gathered size and momentum, and resulted in a wealth of knowledge – which has, in turn, made it hard for people not versed in the field to fully appreciate it. This paper brings scholarly literature on reported speech to bear on slurs and reveals their secret life by dissecting them in the light of reported speech.

- 79** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). *An encyclopedic dictionary of research*. Tehran: Iranian Institute for Encyclopedia Research. [Persian Text]

With well over 1000 encyclopedic entries, this reference book by Salmani Nodoushan (2016) has been written in Persian to help native and non-native speakers of Persian have access to a well-rounded book on theoretical and practical aspects of research. The target readership of the book includes everyone who is involved/interested in academic research. The book includes a glossary of professional research terms and register too.

- 80** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). On the functions of swearing in Persian. *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict*, 4(2), 234-254.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2016) argues that the burgeoning literature on studies of swearing suggests that a precise definition of swearing necessarily involves three features: (a) non-literal meanings, (b) taboo

subjects, and (c) emotions. It also suggested that swearwords fall into one of the three classes: aggressive, cathartic, or social. Driven by a rich corpus of swearwords from Persian, this paper argues that swearing in Persian does not necessarily involve these three features, and that a redefinition of swearing is needed. It then borrows ideas from ethics to suggest that any precise definition of swearing will have to involve the distinction between teleological and deontological ethics. It further envisages a cline for swearing, with teleological ethics at one end and deontological ethics at the other, on which different forms of swearing can be arranged based on the degree to which they lean towards either end.

- 81** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Persian speakers' use of refusal strategies across politeness systems. *PhiN: Philologie Netz*, 76, 61-77.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2016) aimed at investigating the preferred refusal strategies in Persian. 3047 refusals collected by 108 field workers as well as 376 refusals collected through face to face interviews were analyzed and classified according to the descriptions proposed by Liao (1994) and Liao and Bresnahan (1996). The frequencies of the resulting direct and indirect refusal strategies were then used as the data for the current study. Politeness systems as suggested by the model proposed by Scollon and Scollon (2001) as well as refusers' demographic characteristics (i.e., their age, sex, and education level) were used as the independent variables of the study. Kruskal-Wallis H Test and Mann-Whitney U Test results indicated that teen-agers and low-education Persian speakers prefer non-performative refusal strategies. Power relations can also determine whether non-performative strategies are preferred to performative refusals. It was concluded that politeness is a dynamic concept that changes through time and with human generations.

- 82** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Review of the book *The diagnosis of reading in a second or foreign language* by J. C. Alderson, E. L. Haapakangas, A. Huhta, L. Nieminen & R. Ullakonoja. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 26(3), 449-451. (doi: 10.1111/ijal.12156)

Salmani Nodoushan's (2016) book review: This is a critical review of *The Diagnosis of Reading in a Second or Foreign Language* (authored by Alderson et al.). The review will appear in the upcoming issue of *International Journal of Applied Linguistics* (Wiley). The merits of the book make it an outstanding contribution to the field of language assessment, so I strongly recommend that you buy a copy for your own use.

- 83** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Rituals of death as staged communicative acts and pragmemes. In A. Capone & J. L. Mey (Eds.), *Interdisciplinary studies in pragmatics, culture and society* (pp. 925-959). Heidelberg: Springer.

Building on Mey's (2001) notion of pragmatic acts and Capone's (2010) thoughts of rituals of death, this chapter by Salmani Nodoushan (2016) borrows ideas from Mey and Capone to address its main claim that death rituals in Iran are pragmatic acts that fit well in the frame of pragmemes as well as Ostensible Speech Acts (OSAs). It addresses the rituals of death in the

Shiite population of Iran and classifies the speech acts produced in such rites into the three categories of (a) language addressed to Allah, (b) language addressed to the deceased, and (c) language addressed to the grieved relatives of the deceased. Providing samples of speech from any of these situations, the chapter then analyzes them in the framework of conventional speech acts and pragmemes. It compares Shia funerary rites and Catholic death rituals to collude with Capone's (2010) views by arguing that funerary rites function on a psychological plane that aims at providing solace for the grieved relatives of the deceased as well as a social plane that aims at enhancing collective social intentionality. CITATION: Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Rituals of death as staged communicative acts and pragmemes. In A. Capone & J. L. Mey (Eds.), *Interdisciplinary Studies in Pragmatics, Culture and Society*, (pp. 925-959). Heidelberg: Springer.

- 84** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Working on the 'write' path: Improving EFL students' argumentative-writing performance through L1-mediated structural cognitive modification. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 10(4), 131-152.

Based on their scores on a proficiency test, the 894 participants in the study by Salmani Nodoushan (2016) were grouped into three experimental groups (EG) and three control groups (CG). They attempted an argumentative writing task and the Cornell Critical Thinking Test, Form Z (CCTT-Form Z) as the pre-test. While CG participants received no treatment or placebo, EG participants received a three-week workshop treatment aimed at reconstructing their critical thinking and argumentation abilities. Two weeks after the workshop, all participants in all EG and CG groups attempted the same writing task and the Cornell Critical Thinking Test, Form Z (CCTT-Form Z) as the post test. SPANOVA analyses revealed that EFL writing performance will boost if EFL students' are helped to deconstruct, and then reconstruct, their cognitive and thought patterns for appropriate argumentation.

- 85** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2017). Lexemes, practs, and those who have yet to decide. *Linguistik Online*, 81, 77-93.

Mey's (2001) action-theoretic societal pragmatics known as pragmatic act theory nurtures the idea that the explanatory movement in pragmatic theories should go from the outside in (i.e., from actual situational contexts into prior contexts encoded in the utterances used). Kecskes' (2010, 2013) socio-cognitive approach challenges Mey's position, and argues that the explanatory movement should go in both directions: from the outside in and from the inside out. To challenge Mey's view and to nurture his own position, Kecskes resorts to a dialectical socio-cognitive perspective on human communication (Kecskes, 2003, 2008), and uses situation-bound utterances as evidence to support his theory. In this paper, Salmani Nodoushan (2017) provides an overview of both theories and argue in favor of Mey's position.

- 86** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018). A comparative structural move analysis of topical and biographical encyclopedia articles. *Foreign Language Research Journal*, 7(2), 453-470. [Persian Text]

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan (2018) reports on an empirical study that involved the structural move analysis of encyclopedic genre. For purposes of the current study, a corpus of 240 encyclopedic entries (120 topical entries and 120 biographical entries) were randomly chosen from Merriam-Webster's Encyclopedia of Literature. They were then converted into *.txt files and fed into AntMover, the computer software developed for structural move analysis by Anthony (2003). A human coder also coded the texts at two different times with a three-week interval. To avoid random carry-over effect, the human coder used the counter-balanced design in his coding of the texts. Rasmeenin's (2006) and Yang and Allison's (2003) frameworks were employed to identify the obligatory, conventional, and optional moves in the texts. Results indicated that topical and biographical encyclopedic entries do differ in rhetorical structure. The findings of this study can help Iranian encyclopediographers to better understand the standard structure of encyclopedia entries.

- 87** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018). Implementation of the Beghetto-Kaufman-Baer approach to creativity and the four-c developmental trajectory in common core foreign language classrooms. In L. Caudle (Ed.), *Teachers and teaching: Practices, challenges and prospects* (pp. 157-174). New York: Nova Science Publishers, Inc.

Expanding on the recent conception of creativity developed by Beghetto, Kaufman, and Baer (2015), the chapter by Salmani Nodoushan (2018) provides a detailed and comprehensive account of creativity, and how it can be implemented in schools and classrooms. After a brief theoretical overview of creativity and its components, a detailed and precise description of the Four-C Model of Creativity (i.e., mini-c, little-c, Pro-c, and Big-C) is presented. Then, the role of feedback, practice, and time, along with expert companion on the development of a trajectory for creativity, is discussed. The chapter specifically argues how an expert teacher can (a) provide feedback to help students develop personal creativity into everyday creativity, (b) provide practice to help students develop everyday creativity into professional creativity, and (c) provide time for professional creativity to develop into legendary creativity. Further, a discussion of common misperceptions of creativity is presented, and the notion of creative metacognition is discussed. The last section is devoted to the implications of creativity for common core foreign language classrooms.

- 88** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018). Toward a taxonomy of errors in Iranian EFL learners' basic-level writing. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 12(1), 101-116.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan (2018) attempted at classifying common errors found in the written performance of lower- and upper-intermediate Iranian EFL learners. It engaged a rich corpus of EFL writing samples collected over a course of 20 years (between 1992 and 2011) from lower- and upper-intermediate EFL learners studying at various Iranian universities to provide a precise taxonomy of errors in basic-level EFL writing (i.e., single paragraphs and five paragraph essays). A total of 3157 sophomore EFL

learners were included in this study, and from each of them five writing samples were collected. There was a total of 15785 texts in the corpus which contained a total of 5,150,205 words. Corder's (1981) framework for error analysis was implemented, and it was found that basic-level EFL writing errors could best be classified into three major categories: structural, discursive, and cognitive. Classroom procedures and teaching techniques that can help both teachers and learners to overcome the identified error types are discussed.

- 89** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018). Which view of indirect reports do Persian data corroborate? *International Review of Pragmatics*, 10(1), 76-100. (doi: 10.1163/18773109-00901008)

In this paper, Salmani Nodoushan (2018) reviews Davidson's paratactic account of indirect reports, the attacks leveled against it, and the support it received. He then provides data from Persian which seem to support the idea that neither Davidson and his proponents nor his opponents were completely right, and that an adequate theory of indirect reports is doomed to be semantico-pragmatic in nature.

- 90** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2019). A look at the linguistic politeness theory from an Archimedean point. Lecture given on June 22nd, 2019 at the Faculty of Encyclopedia Research, Institute for Humanities and Cultural Studies, Tehran, Iran.

Salmani Nodoushan's (2019) lecture given on June 22, 2019, at the Institute for Humanities and Cultural Studies, Tehran, Iran. [Language of Presentation: Persian]

- 91** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2019). Clearing the mist: The border between linguistic politeness and social etiquette. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 13(2), 109-120.

Even some of the biggest names in pragmatics and politeness oftentimes confuse social etiquette with linguistic politeness. Salmani Nodoushan (2019) argues that he was recently invited to examine a PhD thesis at a famous university in a developed country, and it came to him as a shock to realize that neither the PhD candidate nor her thesis supervisors had noticed the difference between these two concepts. Since a clear understanding of rudimentary concepts is fundamental to any research in any field of science, and pragmatics and politeness are not exceptions, this paper aims at putting linguistic politeness in its right frame. It first reviews the historical development of modern pragmatics from an Archimedean point; then, it sets politeness theory in its right place inside pragmatics. Finally, it draws a line between social etiquette and linguistic politeness and argue that junior (and some senior) researchers working on politeness need to be very careful not to confuse the two, or their claims are doomed to be invalid.

- 92** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2020). *The concise encyclopedia of cultural studies*. Tehran: Institute for Humanities and Cultural Studies. [Persian Text]

This work by Salmani Nodoushan (2020) is the compilation of a Persian reference book on cultural studies. The language of text is Persian.

- 93 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Alavi, S. M. (2004). *APA style and research report writing*. Tehran: Zabankadeh publications.

APA Style and Research Report Writing was designed by Salmani Nodoushan and Alavi (2004) to foster in undergraduate students the skills they need for success in their research courses. The book consists of three distinct sections: APA style, Library Research, and Reports and Theses. Section one presents the basic concepts of APA style in five chapters: general presentation, tables and figures, footnotes and quotations, references, and APA intricacies. Since the Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association published by the American Psychological Association (5th ed.) is a large and very detailed book, many undergraduate students find it a bit intimidating to use. Therefore, the five chapters of this section have been prepared in such a way as to make the task of complying with APA style easier for undergraduate students. A step-by-step, user-friendly, and interactive guide to the major aspects of Microsoft Word XP that students need to know is also incorporated to this section so that they can use the software for typing their final research report. Section two is composed of two chapters: The Library, and Note Keeping. Chapter six discusses the rudiments and the basic concepts of library research. It covers such topics as the sources available in the library, different library search methods, the importance of library research, and a few important hints for the library researchers. The focus of chapter seven is on the most popular library search method, note keeping. Two types of notes are discussed: bibliographical notes, and subject notes. Examples of each type are provided. In addition, the intricacies of note taking for each type are elaborated on. Plagiarism is discussed as the major pitfall in library research. Finally, a few hints are provided for the library research worker as to how they should approach the task of paraphrasing. Section three, too, is composed of two chapters: The Research Report, and The Thesis. Chapter eight focuses on the detailed format that a modest research report should have. The different sections of the research report are discussed, along with visual illustrations to foster in undergraduate students the skills they need for writing their research reports. The final few pages of the chapter elaborate on the differences between student research reports and journal papers. Chapter nine is most useful for graduate students. A brief synopsis of the differences that exist between short research reports and masters' theses or PhD dissertations is presented. The discussions of the chapter are enriched with visual illustrations that are helpful to the graduate student in the process of writing his thesis or dissertation.

- 94 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Allami, H. (2011). Supportive discourse moves in Persian requests. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 5(2), 65-94.

This paper by Salmani Nodoushan and Allami (2011) reports the findings of a study designed to investigate the types of supportive discourse moves employed by Persian speakers in their Requestive Speech Acts. 372 respondents took a Discourse Completion Test (DCT) with six scenarios ranging from formal to informal degrees of Perceived Situational Seriousness,

and returned 2232 Requestive Speech Acts (RSAs). The acts were then analyzed according to models proposed by Færch and Kasper (1989), Blum-Kulka, et al. (1989), and Scollon and Scollon (2001). Results, after analysis of the data, indicated that Persian speakers use external and internal discourse moves to negotiate face in RSAs. It was concluded that Perceived Situational Seriousness was the determining factor in the choice of the type and number of discourse moves in a given RSA.

- 95 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Birjandi, P. (2005). *An introduction to phonetics*. Tehran: Zabankadeh publications.

According to Salmani Nodoushan and Birjandi (2005), a major difficulty facing almost any foreign language learner is the achievement of acceptable pronunciation which marks his success in mastering the language. Many EFL learners master such aspects of language as syntax, semantics, morphology, and even pragmatics to the point of native-like competence, but fail to master phonology. This is partly because of the physiological constraints that make the pronunciation of a foreign or second language sound different from that of the native language of the speakers, and partly due to the lack of appropriate training in phonology courses. Phonetics is designed to support EFL learners in achieving native-like pronunciation. The first chapter deals with the history of phonology and phonetics and provides a brief overview of the impact of philosophy and psychology on the emergence of phonology. The second chapter defines the notion of phoneme, describes IPA phonetic alphabet, and distinguishes between broad and narrow transcriptions. Chapters three and four provide an in-depth account of traditional and systematic articulatory phonetics respectively. Chapter five discusses the place of suprasegmentals in phonology. Chapter six seeks to explain phonemics. Chapter seven provides a brief introduction to the rudiments of acoustic or physical phonetics. Finally, chapter eight introduces the reader to the notion of auditory phonetics. The book is designed for use in undergraduate classes of phonology and phonetics. The fifth chapter is also useful for students of conversation classes. Teachers at high school level may also find the fifth chapter valuable. The step by step approach of the book towards its subject matter makes it is easy for the reader to follow the line of discussion without the help of a phonology teacher.

- 96 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Daftarifard, P. (2011). Globalized classroom, emancipatory competence, and critical pedagogy: A paradigm shift. In R. V. Nata (Ed.), *Progress in education* (vol. 26, pp. 147-162). New York: Nova Science Publishers, Inc.

This chapter by Salmani Nodoushan and Daftarifard (2011) aims at depicting critical pedagogy and claims that critical pedagogy is the new paradigm that has emerged out of sociopolitical aspects of language teaching.

- 97 Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Garcia Laborda, J. (2014). The bilingual self or selves? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 8(3), 107-116.

A concise but strong review of the literature on bilinguals' perception of 'self' led (Salmani Nodoushan & Garcia Laborda, 2014) to the question of whether

bilinguals perceive themselves as different or the same people when they function in different languages. 183 participants (N =183) randomly assigned to two half-groups took both the English and Persian versions of the Self Concept Scale (SCS) in two counter-balanced administration sessions with a time interval of 3 weeks. Results after analysis of the data using descriptive and inferential statistics indicated that Iranian-Americans have a more realistic self concept when they function in English than when they function in Persian. Their self concepts in English and Persian do not match. Moreover, the female Iranian-American shows a larger discrepancy in her English and Persian self concepts than her male counterpart. This indicates that females are more open to alienation than males are. The results of this study lend empirical support to claims made by previous researchers that bilinguals have a kind of split personality. It was concluded that a bilingual is not a unique person who assumes different identities when he functions in the different languages he knows, but that the bilingual possess two different guises or selves which are language-specific and are used in accordance with the language the bilingual speaks at any given point in time.

- 98** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Khakbaz, N. (2011). Theses 'Discussion' sections: A structural move analysis. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 5(3), 111-132.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan and Khakbaz (2011) aimed at finding the probable differences between the move structure of Iranian MA graduates' thesis discussion subgenres and those of their non-Iranian counterparts, on the one hand, and those of journal paper authors, on the other. It also aimed at identifying the moves that are considered obligatory, conventional, or optional by Iranian MA graduates. 46 (N = 46) masters thesis 'discussion' sections taken randomly from a pool of 93 discussions written in English by Iranian EFL students comprised the corpus for this study. The AntMover software as well as two human coders identified and coded the moves found in the corpus. The resulting move frequencies were compared to those of Rasmeenin's (2006) study as well as Yang and Allison's (2003) framework using a set of Mann-Whitney U tests as well as One-Sample t-Tests. Results indicated that there is a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian versus non-Iranian EFL students. There was also a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian EFL students and the discussion sub-genre of journal papers published in internationally recognized applied-linguistic journals. Obligatory, conventional, and optional moves were also identified. It was concluded that academic writing teachers need to focus on move structures and make their students move-sensitive.

- 99** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Khakbaz, N. (2012). *Theses discussions: A structural move analysis*. Berlin: LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.

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identifying the moves that are considered obligatory, conventional, or optional by Iranian MA graduates. 46 (N = 46) masters thesis 'discussion' sections taken randomly from a pool of 93 discussions written in English by Iranian EFL students comprised the corpus for this study. The AntMover software as well as two human coders identified and coded the moves found in the corpus. The resulting move frequencies were compared to those of Rasmeenin's (2006) study as well as Yang and Allison's (2003) framework using a set of Mann-Whitney U tests as well as One-Sample t-Tests. Results indicated that there is a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian versus non-Iranian EFL students. There was also a significant difference in the move frequency of the discussion sub-genre of MA theses written by Iranian EFL students and the discussion sub-genre of journal papers published in internationally recognized applied-linguistic journals. Obligatory, conventional, and optional moves were also identified. It was concluded that academic writing teachers need to focus on move structures and make their students move-sensitive.

- 100** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Mohiyedin Ghomshei, G. R. (2014). Iconicity of cohesion in Persian causative constructions. *Linguistik Online*, 68, 29-42.

This paper by Salmani Nodoushan and Mohiyedin Ghomshei (2014) tries to show that Persian causative constructions are not only iconic in nature but also employ iconicity of cohesion in their syntactic structures productively. It starts with a description of iconicity and specifically focuses on the notion of conceptual distance as discussed by Haiman (1983). It then briefly reviews the formal typology of causative constructions (i. e., lexical, morphological, and periphrastic) and summarizes the ideas proposed by Comrie (1989), Dixon (2000), Shibatani (1976), and Talmy (2003) to come up with a list of, and a table for, the semantic properties of causative constructions (i. e., directness, coercion, control, manipulation, separability, and clause structure). The paper then presents tangible evidence and examples from Persian to claim that the linguistic distance observed between [Vcause] and [Veffect] in different types of Persian causative constructions mirrors the conceptual distance between them, and concludes that the iconic nature of causative constructions in Persian can be explained on the basis of the principle of iconicity of cohesion. It lends support to the universality of the principles of functional-cognitive linguistics and shows that iconicity theory still has a high potential for explaining form-meaning relations in different syntactic structures.

- 101** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Montazeran, H. (2012). The book review genre: A structural move analysis. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 6(1), 1-30.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan and Montazeran (2012) aimed at showing whether native, ESL and EFL book review authors differed in terms of types of rhetorical moves they employ in the reviews they write. 60 book reviews (N = 60) from applied linguistics journals were randomly selected from a pool of 87 book reviews published in *Asian EFL Journal*, *ESP*, *System*, and *TESOL Quarterly* between 2004 and 2010. The reviews were converted into *.txt files and submitted to the AntMover software for move analysis. Two human

coders used the Motta Roth's (1995) framework for the analysis of the moves. The intercoder reliability of the study was estimated through a Spearman's rho at .819 (rho = .819), and the convergent validity of the instruments by another Spearman's rho at .782 (rho = .782). The data were submitted to a set of Kruskal-Wallis H Test. The results of the study indicated that writers' linguistic backgrounds have a statistically significant role in their choice of book review moves and move structures. It was also found that book reviews fall into the two categories of 'informative' and 'evaluative' reviews with the difference between the two lying in the presence or absence of writers' focused evaluation of the books under review in terms of their advantages and/or disadvantages.

- 102** Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Pashapour, A. (2016). Critical pedagogy, rituals of distinction, and true professionalism. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 13(1), 29-43.

The study by Salmani Nodoushan and Pashapour (2016) sought to critically address the practice of rituals of distinction in nation-wide educational milieus to see if such practices can produce generations of underdeveloped and deprived learners. Data were collected over a course of two years from north Korea, Pakistan, Zimbabwe, Venezuela, and Somalia. A total of 419 teachers, educators and students from these countries responded to email communication, were observed through participant observation, or were interviewed through skype; they provided descriptions and examples of educational settings and practices in their respective countries. The data were then analyzed qualitatively and in the light of (a) Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives, (b) Maslow's hierarchy of needs, and (c) Feuerstein's notion of 'culturally deprived' learners. It was concluded that, education systems in countries ruled by ideological or ideocratic regimes, intentionally and actively deprive learner generations of quality education with the aim of hammering whole societies into the shape which will guarantee their own grip on political power. Drawing on the concepts of 'small-c culture' and 'capital-c culture' from relevant literature, the paper argues that despotic regimes, by virtue of their education systems, mainly betray their most obedient citizens who are committed to them and whereby deprive them of true professionalism.